

Research Article

An External Environment Situation Analysis of Bangladesh-China Towards Health Collaboration Under Obor Initiative

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Background In a rapidly globalizing world with increasing health and epidemiologic transitions, the international community and multilateralism have become highly active, coordinated and robust. To face the challenges of health and epidemiologic transitions, ageing and globalization challenges, collaborative diplomacy on health security have become more vital than ever in not only saving lives and improving public health but also in improving and providing long-lasting benefits to both worlds' poorest and developed countries, the PEST analysis method, which is mostly used in the field of economic management to analyze the external macro environment of specific countries and regions that need to be considered when formulating corporate strategies. The PEST analysis includes analysis of the four macro forces of the political, economic, social, and technological environments of the country.

Methods This study was based on literature review, secondhand data from the website, Ministry of health Bangladesh and face to face interview with the key person.

Results Bangladesh external environment is still far lower than China in every indicator of political, economic, social and technological. Most of the indicators show upwards slowly which is a good sign for one country. Bangladesh relatively weak indicators are innovation, infrastructure, low Technology, legal and administrative framework indicators. As well as China political environment is also ranking in the lower position. China has shown a good development trend in the innovation field. Although Bangladesh has a poor foundation in terms of innovation, investment in research and development has begun to yield benefits, and there will be wider room for progress and development in the future.

Conclusion Bangladesh is struggling in Poor infrastructure and Poor Policy, Therefore, China should strengthen policy guidance, continuous capital and human investment, continuously enrich science and technology research and development activities, and enhance independent innovation capabilities.

Keywords: PEST Analysis, OBOR, Health collaboration, Bangladesh-china

Introduction

„One belt, one road“ is a development strategy initiated and planned by the Chinese government in 2013 to enhance regional connectivity and to integrate the Silk Road Spirit – "peace and cooperation, openness and inclusiveness, mutual learning and mutual benefit" of the countries along the Belt and Road [1]. In a rapidly globalizing world with increasing health and epidemiologic transitions, the international community and multilateralism have become highly active, coordinated and robust. to face the challenges of health and epidemiologic transitions, ageing and globalization challenges, collaborative diplomacy on health security have become more vital than ever in not only saving lives and improving public health but also in improving and providing long-lasting benefits to both worlds' poorest and developed countries [2].

If we take a brief look at the background of China-Bangladesh bilateral relations, it can be assumed that their traditional relations were based on trade and military cooperation. Bangladesh is the third-largest trade partner of China in South Asia [3], in October, 2016, which was widely dubbed as a “historic state visit”, beginning of a “new horizon”, or “a new historical starting point” of China-Bangladesh relations. China-Bangladesh relations in the twenty-first century is the cooperation in regional as well as sub-regional connectivity. the “Belt and Road Initiative” (BRI) in 2013 attaches greater importance to the enhancement of China-Bangladesh bilateral relations in that regard [4].

PEST analysis of China and Bangladesh

Harvard professor **Francis Aguilar** is thought to be the creator of PEST Analysis. The PEST analysis is an analysis of the external macro-environment. Francis J. Aguilar (1967) who discusses ‘ETPS’ first. Later on, In 1999, American scholars Johnson G and Scholes K proposed the PEST analysis method, which is mostly used in the field of economic management to analyze the external macro environment of specific countries and regions that need to be considered when formulating corporate strategies. The PEST analysis includes analysis of the four macro forces of the political, economic, social, and technological environments of the country and region [5]. The political environment mainly includes the political system and system of a country or region, laws and regulations, the attitude and effectiveness of the government. The economic environment refers to the general situation of national economic development,

international and domestic economic situation and development trends, including income factors, consumption expenditures, industrial structure, economic growth rate, currency supply, bank interest rates, government expenditures, etc. factor. The key strategic elements that make up the economic environment include GDP, market mechanisms, and market demand. The social and cultural environment refers to the sum of values, religious beliefs, customs and ethics, which have been formed under the social form, and is related to the state and value orientation of a society. Any country or region is in a certain social and cultural environment, and the choice of war is inevitably influenced and restricted by the social and cultural environment in which it is located. The technical environment includes the current level of development and development of science and technology, technological change and technological breakthroughs, and the interaction between technology and politics, economic and economic, and social environment. It has the characteristics of rapid change, large change, and great influence.

Materials and methods

The political environment mainly includes the political system and system of a country or region, laws and regulations, the attitude and effectiveness of the government. The economic environment refers to the general situation of national economic development, international and domestic economic situation and development trends, including income factors, consumption expenditures, industrial structure, economic growth rate, currency supply, bank interest rates, government expenditures, etc. factor. The key strategic elements that make up the economic environment include GDP, market mechanisms, and market demand. The social and cultural environment refers to the sum of values, religious beliefs, customs and ethics, which have been formed under the social form, and is related to the state and value orientation of a society. Any country or region is in a certain social and cultural environment, and the choice of war is inevitably influenced and restricted by the social and cultural environment in which it is located. The technical environment includes the current level of development and development of science and technology, technological change and technological breakthroughs, and the interaction between technology and politics, economic and economic, and social environment. It has the characteristics of rapid change, large change, and great influence.

PEST Analysis was examined to demonstrate the background of Bangladesh and China Political, Economical, Social and Technological issue. The study was based on literature review,

secondhand data from website and PI. The political situation is mainly based on Voice and Accountability, Political stability and violence avoidance, Government effectiveness, Quality of regulation, rule of law, Corruption control. This data are mainly from “world government indicators” the economical situation this study used the data of Legal and administrative structures, infrastructure, macroeconomic environment, health and primary education, higher education and training, goods market efficiency and labour market efficiency Or market efficiency, financial market development, technical readability, market size, business integrity and innovation.” The global competitiveness index (GCI) 2018.” the Social environment and the Technological situation used the data from “World bank indicators”. The proportion of labour force in agriculture, industry and service industry can reflect the current situation of science and technology in the country. The high proportion of the rural population and an unbalanced distribution of labour force will restrict the development of science and technology innovation level. This study mainly focused on the External situation of both countries to provide a clear understanding of Similarities and common weaknesses to build a future health-related collaboration strategy between China and Bangladesh.

Result

In the past decade, China’s political stability and absence of violence indicator have been relatively stable with a slight decline in 2012 which was 25.59% wherein 2019 it's increased to 36.67%, China rapidly increasing in this indicator. Where Bangladesh is still far away compare to China. In this indicator, Bangladesh was 26.6% in the year of 1996 and that was the highest value till now. Which dropped till 4.37% in the year of 2005 after that its rapidly increased to 16.67% in 2014 But in 2017 it went lower to 10.48%, which is not stable yet. The government's effectiveness index continued to be occupied by China in the past 21 years. Although there was a slight downward trend in 2007-2013 with 55.45% to 68.28% in 2017. in Bangladesh, it was 38.86% in 1998 but its comparatively getting downwards till 19.12% in 2005. in 2017 which is 22.12%. the gap between the two countries is too big and wide day by day. Bangladesh still needs to work so hard on their Government effectiveness index.

Figure 1: World Governance Indicators in 2017-2018 [6]

From the perspective of regulatory quality indicators, China was slightly higher than the east Asia regional average (48.16%) in 2007 where china was (50.97%), but it has been declining for ten years, in 2017 which is 48.56%.compare with Bangladesh still so far from China. The lowest value was 12.32% in 2004. After that slowly upwards to 22.12% in 2016 and which is 20.67% in 2017. The rule of law indicators, China's legal indicators have fluctuated more obviously in the past decade. In 2008 china was 39.9% following up to 40.765 in 2010 and

slightly downwards. China maintains a good follow up compared to Bangladesh. Where Bangladesh was 15.79% in 2004 and slowly increase to 27.7% in 2011 up to 28.37% in 2017, where china is 44.71% in 2017. still have a big gap between 2 countries.

In terms of corruption control indicators, China fluctuated from 2007 to 2010, but it grew steadily from 2012 to 2016 till 49.04%. and slightly down in 2017 to 46.63%.in the past decades Bangladesh was worse in corruption control but from the year 2007 its started increasing from 13.59% to 22.84% in 2015 and 19.23% in 2017. Based on the analysis of 12 indicators of the global competitiveness index in 2018, in 12 indicators China is in the leading position (Figure 2). Compared with Bangladesh, China has obvious advantages in market size and macroeconomic environment also growing in Health and primary education. Bangladesh advantage indicators are also close to China in some indicators. Bangladesh relatively weak indicators are innovation, infrastructure, low Technology, legal and administrative framework indicators need to be further improved.

Figure 2: Global competitiveness of China and Bangladesh 2018 [7, 8]

The two countries are comparatively close to each other in terms of Goods market efficiency, Financial market development, Macroeconomic Environment However, the low score of innovation indicators is the common short board of the two countries, which urgently needs to

create a suitable innovation environment and increase innovation competitiveness to better drive economic development. And with the growth of GDP, the development stage of the country will change, and the weight of innovation and complexity factors will continue to increase, that is, the defects of innovation indicators will be magnified. China and Bangladesh both are socialist countries. They have similarities in terms of governance concepts, goals, and social values. social system and similar ideology are conducive to the friendly cultural exchanges and in-depth cooperation between the two countries.[9] China is a country with vast land and objects, and is the world's largest population country. Bangladesh has a large population, has the highest population density among the two countries, and its population structure is in the golden ratio for this small country (Table 1).

Table 1 list of the social environment in China and Bangladesh.

Country	Total area (km ²)	Population (million) 2018	official language	Nationality	Faith
China	959.7	138.4	Standard Chinese or Mandarin	Han Chinese 91.6%, Zhuang 1.3%, other 7.1%	Buddhist 18.2%, Christian 5.1%, Muslim 1.8%, folk religion 21.9%, unaffiliated 52.2%
Bangladesh	14.85	15.9	Bangla 98.8% other 1.2%	Bangladeshi	Muslim 89.1%, Hindu 10%, other 0.9%

Datalink: World Bank- Databank indicators [10, 11]

In this study, two indicators, the proportion of the rural population and the labour force-by occupation, are selected to evaluate the technological environment of each country. Among them, the occupation labour rate refers to the proportion of the labour force allocated in different occupation fields. Agriculture includes agriculture, fishery, and forestry; industry includes mining, manufacturing, energy production and construction; the service industry includes government activities, communications, transportation, finance and other economic activities that do not produce material products. Compared with the proportion of the rural population in China,

Bangladesh, South Asia and the world (Figure 3), China has the largest agricultural population among 2 countries, accounting for 27.70% of the total population. The proportion of the rural population in Bangladesh is 63.40%, [12] higher than China, the proportion of the rural population in China is slightly lower than the global average, at 40.80%.

The distribution of the labor force in China's agriculture, industry and service industry is relatively uniform. the proportion of the service industry is the highest (43.5%), lower than that in Bangladesh (56.50%) where the global average is (45.0%). Bangladesh industrial labour force accounts for 29.30%, is the highest among the two countries China's industrial labour share (28.80%), and higher than the global average (23.5%). The proportion of agricultural labour force in China is the highest (27.70%), Bangladesh is (14.20%) and both are lower than the global average (31.5%). Bangladesh the first productivity of economic development is ready-made garments, remittances and the domestic agricultural sector., which is closely related to their limited scientific and technological development [13] China's economic structure is supported by three major industries.

Figure 3: occupation labour rate and proportion of the rural population in 2018

Data link: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator>

Discussion

Most of the indicators of Bangladesh political environment rank low. Although the growth trend in the past decade is acceptable, the overall political situation is raising slowly. Except for voice and accountability indicators and political stability other indicators are low. A stable political environment plays a guaranteed role for the development of the national economy, and is also a necessary prerequisite for winning investment and cooperation of other countries. The economy of Bangladesh is a developing market economy. Bangladesh is one of the world's fastest-growing economy. In the decade since 2004, Bangladesh averaged a GDP growth of 6.5%, that has been largely driven by its exports of readymade garments, remittances and the domestic agricultural sector. Bangladesh economy develops steadily and rapidly, and its global competitiveness ranks ahead steadily. It's the 39th largest in the world in nominal terms, and 29th largest by purchasing power parity; it is classified among the Next Eleven emerging market middle income economies and a frontier market. The Bangladesh government also recognizes that there are still some shortcomings in the economy, such as lack of innovation and incomplete infrastructure, and formulates corresponding policy objectives to focus on solving problems, Bangladesh has a greater advantage in-market scale. The competitive advantage of the labor force is reflected in three aspects: a large proportion of labour force, stable supply of labour force in the future and low labour cost. Bangladesh and China have profound cultural origins, and there are many similarities, which will become the ties and bridges for the establishment of cooperative relations. There are some differences between China and Bangladesh also in terms of religious beliefs and cultural concepts, which will inevitably may affect the exchange and cooperation.

Bangladesh and China have a lower international ranking in terms of political environment indicators. The government's leading role in cooperation is significant, and the signing of various rules and agreements needs to be promoted by the government. China in terms of the power of speech and responsibility have put forward new requirements for the governments. Bangladesh government also need to take a proper step in other political environment indicators as the ranking is still low. Innovation is the common shortcoming of the two countries in the economic environment. The innovation indicators of two countries ranked last among the twelve economic indicators, which directly lowered the competitiveness scores of the countries. And with the development of the economy, the lack of innovation will become

more obvious to the economic constraints, and this problem needs to be solved urgently. With the reform of the scientific and technological system and the gradual establishment of the national innovation system, China has shown a good development trend in the innovation field. Although Bangladesh has a poor foundation in terms of innovation, investment in research and development has begun to yield benefits, and there will be wider room for progress and development in the future. China attaches great importance to the construction of national scientific and technological innovation capabilities, and has continuously increased its investment in scientific and technological resources and scientific and technological manpower, but there is still a problem of weak independent innovation capabilities. However, domestic investment in science, technology, and innovation Bangladesh has been ranked the least innovative country in Asia, which is less than 1% of their GDP, and there is a problem of excessive dependence on foreign investment. Also, Bangladesh is struggling in Poor infrastructure and Poor Policy, Therefore, China should strengthen policy guidance, continuous capital and human investment, continuously enrich science and technology research and development activities, and enhance independent innovation capabilities. In the future cooperation between the three countries, more innovative cooperation areas and projects should be developed. The cooperation mechanism should be coordinated and complementary on the existing basis, so that scientific and technological innovation becomes a strong support for economic and social development.

Conclusion

Due to the close economic and trade exchanges between the two sides and the differences in industrial structure and resource utilization, China and Bangladesh are economically interdependent and complement each other in trade. The long-standing traditional mutual trust between China and Bangladesh are both the basis for cooperation and the guarantee for long-term cooperation. The above characteristics have consolidated the friendly and cooperative relations between China and Bangladesh, and also put forward requirements and expectations for future multi-level and multi-field cooperation. The infrastructure construction and technological development in Bangladesh are still at a low level. The economic base still has a gap with China. But Bangladesh is now considered a “Development Miracle” and has emerged as one of the fastest-growing economies of the world. Most importantly, China-Bangladesh “strategic

partnership of cooperation,” instead of “comprehensive partnership of cooperation,” inject new impetus into the relationship. This new type of strategic partnership signifies intensive engagements and heightened cooperation on all the issues related to mutual interest and common prosperity, such as political, economic, cultural, and security issues at bilateral, regional and global levels along with other regional and international affairs.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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